

COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT NON -PHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASIS OF DEVELOPING PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

The peculiarities of the development of the information society determine the modernization of the education system in higher education. Modern society is interested in specialists who are ready to take independent responsibility for the decisions made, are able to set goals and choose a way to achieve them based on their own value priorities, thereby proving their own individuality. This article highlights new approaches in teaching foreign languages and aims at detecting ESP students' pragmatic ability, on the example of recognizing and producing the speech acts of warning, finding ways of teaching them, and attempting to find possible solutions. In present research, we tried to indicate potential differences in the use of the speech act of warning in English between Uzbek and American social contexts.

Young professionals in any field of activity should have the ability to realistically assess their capabilities, their professional activity and its results. At the present stage of the development of higher education in non-linguistic universities, there is a certain uniformity of requirements for the training of specialists in a foreign language.

Existing curricula and standards are not keeping up with the rapidly changing world. Unfortunately, they do not always take into account the specifics of universities, professional and personal needs of students, do not pay special attention to the training of a student, a

future specialist, processing a large amount of information. Teachers of non-linguistic universities often independently refine the proposed recommendations. They are forced to develop the most optimal ways, effective methods of teaching students a foreign language at all stages, taking into account the cognitive needs of students, the peculiarities of their cognitive sphere.

A foreign language is one of the most popular subjects in non-linguistic universities. Knowledge and proficiency in one or two foreign languages gives the student the opportunity not only to receive professionally significant information, but also to learn the peculiarities of the culture

of the country of the studied language, expand their own horizons, get acquainted with the production sphere of the countries of the studied language, form the ability to make new, independent, non-standard decisions, undergo advanced training in the country of the studied language.

In world educational practice, the concept of competence acts as a central, a kind of "nodal" concept, because personality competence:

- firstly, it combines the intellectual and practical components of education;
- secondly, the concept of competence is based on the ideology of interpretation of the content of education formed "from the result" ("standard at the exit");
- thirdly, the competence of an individual has an integrative nature, since it incorporates a number of homogeneous or closely related knowledge and experience related to broad spheres of culture and activity (informational, legal, etc.).

A person's competence has a certain structure, the components of which are related to a person's ability to solve various problems in everyday, professional or social life. The structure of personal competence includes: competence in the field of independent cognitive activity; in the field of civil and social activity; in the field of social and labor competence in the household sphere; in the field of cultural and leisure activities. Among the knowledge and practical experience formed in the process of achieving a certain level of competence by a person are the skills of

self-education, critical thinking, independent work, self-organization and self-control, teamwork, the ability to predict the results and possible consequences of different solutions, establish causal relationships, find, formulate and solve problems.

As we know classroom environments worldwide are commonly teacher-centered, structured to complete the syllabus with little time during lessons to facilitate the practice of language where learners are involved in comprehension and production of pragmatic meaning. And the opportunities to use the target language in situations that approach real-world conversation are limited. For this reason, I realized that it is important to start investigating the integration of pragmatic competence in foreign language teaching. Since the ultimate aim of learning languages is communication, it is important to conduct a study that contributes to facilitating this aim with the help of pragmatics. This aim seems even more indispensable in contexts where little emphasis is given to developing communicative competence, in particular ESP contexts.

Pragmatics and teaching English cannot be separated since they shared one important aspect dealing with communication. Teaching language in general and teaching English in specific should involve an awareness of meaning in context. Teachers should be aware of their pragmatic competence to develop students' pragmatic awareness. The most important knowledge to be taught to students is the rules to use language for communication. Students are demanded to own the communication skills that can support

them as the part of the society. Not only in the classroom, should students also be able to communicate effectively with language outside classroom or the real world. Therefore, English teaching is supposed to have the main role to carry out the main purpose of language teaching which is to develop students' communicative competence. One way can be done is to integrate English language teaching and pragmatics in the classroom. Teacher is required then to own pragmatic knowledge and competence in teaching English to his or her students.

Nowadays pragmatic competence is so important. Lack of pragmatic competence may result to problem in communication such as miscommunication and misunderstanding. The utterances in miscommunication or misunderstanding may be considered rude insults. This is the main reason why students need to learn and to have the pragmatic competence to support their communication abilities. In order to teach that pragmatic competence to students, teacher, then, has to own this competence. He or she has to understand and aware of pragmatics knowledge and pragmatics competence.

I lead Practical English classes to 1st year students in Chemical faculty and the above given lesson also was conducted with the same learners. My usual classes include in itself 20 students with different level of English as B1 and A2. The students in the group are supportive and friendly with each other. CLT approach based tasks do not always work well with all students of this group because of the differences on the levels. I have English class with them twice a week. Usually during the pre and

post stages of the lesson, which are built on practicing and discussions, the 10 students are very active, while the other 5 speak whenever they are asked to. The rest of the group stays passive during the lesson. So for the chosen lesson plan, in order to make all students speak and being active during the activities, I had applied interactive techniques, in which all students tried to use the target language during the activities.

I should say in some situations during the teaching and learning process at the department, background knowledge of the students in an interaction, for example, is rarely taken into consideration. The students are treated in a similar way regardless of their familiarity with the task. The ability to communicate and the ability to be understood are the most important parts of learning a new language and background knowledge of the students is influenced by the speaker's language and affected the extent of information that is provided.

And the content is ESP for Chemical technology learners and considering the significance of ESP for these learners we should organize the lessons in a thought-provoking way. In order to reinforce the teaching of ESP, I have included various visual aids in the form of picture with signs, descriptions of pictures, video demonstrations and poster presentations in my lesson, especially to provoke a speech. These study materials have been very helpful for my students as chemistry students need authentic things as the visuals are huge they seem to be applicable for ESP teaching especially for improving conversational skills.(Picture 1.)

Picture 1.Warning signs

And I felt that my lesson was successful because every student could speak in this area, even though there were students with a low level of knowledge. I would say that the visual communication components used by the teacher in the class not only make it easier for students to acquire knowledge and skills, but also teach them how to successfully apply visual effects in their communication. But one drawback for me was that it took a long time to prepare and find effective visual aids for the lesson.

In linguistics, pragmatic competence is the ability to use language effectively in a contextually appropriate manner. Pragmatic competence is a fundamental aspect of more general communicative

competence. Pragmatic competence is understood as knowledge of the linguistic resources available in a given language for the implementation of certain illocutions, knowledge of the sequential aspects of speech acts, and, finally, knowledge of the appropriate contextual use of the linguistic resources of a particular language. And people while interpreting words/sentences add their own intentions to these words/sentences. Thus, words/sentences in their use may change their primary/dictionary meanings. Pragmatics deals with “what people mean by their utterances than what the words or phrases in those utterances might mean by themselves” (Yule, 1996, p.3). Pragmatics mainly deals with what is beyond the

dictionary meanings of statements; in other words, it is about what is actually meant with an utterance based on the norms and conventions of a particular society, or context, in which conversation takes place. Therefore, having a good command of the conventions enables the speaker to establish and maintain effective and appropriate communication as well as understanding each other clearly (Yule, 1996) and this ability is generally referred as pragmatic competence (cited in Takkaç Tulgar, A.2016).

In simple terms, Pragmatics is about culture, communication, and in the case of second languages, about intercultural communication. In order for second language learners to acquire pragmatic competence, they need to acquire cultural understanding and communication skills.

Furthermore, teaching pragmatic competence is one of the most neglected aspects in English language teaching in most countries where English is taught as a foreign language. Teaching English to FL students should involve not only familiarizing learners with the sounds, vocabulary, and grammar of the TL, but also helping them to use the TL effectively through making them acquainted with the pragmatic rules that govern the appropriate combination of utterances and communicative functions. And the responsibility of teaching pragmatic aspects of language use falls on the teachers. However, as language teachers, we face certain challenges. These include lack of adequate materials and training, which are the result of lack of emphasis on pragmatic issues in ESP/EFL teaching methodology.

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